

**DESIGNING EFFECTIVE WIRELESS SECURITY AND FORENSICS
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ABSTRACT

Gone are the days when everyone relied on a physical connection to a local area network (LAN), using ethernet cables, before they could communicate with each other and ultimately share resources. The limitation of having to physically connect to a network has been well obviated by the introduction of wireless technology. In a wireless network, communication is done through radio waves, and hence devices do not need to be physically connected to the network before they can communicate. This flexibility has been well embraced by many and has also led to the rapid adoption of wireless network implementation in organizations. However, the flexibility and portability of this system rather allows it to be very susceptible to attacks, as such vulnerabilities can be easily exploited without the attacker being physically plugged into the network. In this paper, we take a close look at the security threats that plague the wireless communication network, while looking at the threats that might be faced at each level of the protocol layer. We also probe into the already existing security requirements for wireless networks and finally dive into the various mitigation techniques that exist. Our aim is to come to a common ground; which is to effectively provide the good requirements that these mitigation techniques or mechanisms must meet in order to be classified as effective - we would arrive at these by studying the already implemented solutions, and looking at ways of possible improvements on such.

The paper is organized as follows: in section 1, we introduce the basic concepts as they relate to the world of wireless networks, touching a little about how things have evolved. Section 2 dives more into the background of wireless networks, exploring the basic requirements of the security of a wireless system, and enumerating some key concepts that need to be understood. In section 3, we look at the security requirements of a wireless network. and explore various protocols of wireless networks in section 4. In section 5, we look at the threats that plague wireless networks and the mitigations against these attacks are considered in section 6. In section 7, we state some of the common grounds among these techniques and bring the work to a conclusion in section 8.

Keywords:

LAN, WLAN, AP, WEP, WPA/WPA2, EAP, RADIUS, QoS, OSI

[1] INTRODUCTION

A computer network is known as the interconnection of devices for the purpose of communication and data sharing; examples of network devices would include printer, laptops, desktop, access point, etc. Basically, the system can either be wired and wireless.

In a wired network system, each component of the network such as a laptop has to be physically connected to the network; without this connection there is no way connection can be made. In a wireless system, however, there is no need for a physical connection to the network. Usually an access point is what controls the network system, and

network devices can connect without being physically plugged into the network. Wi-Fi is the name of the popular networking technology that uses radio waves to provide wireless high-speed internet and network connection. [2] The fact that a wired network system lacks such flexibility and portability is its major demerits, though in terms of

being secure, such systems are generally very less vulnerable to attacks. On the contrary, in a wireless network there is room for flexibility and portability as the network devices do not have to be physically connected or

plugged into the network in order to have access. This is what makes wireless networks very open to many vulnerabilities and security threats.

Therefore, the adoption of wireless network systems has become quite prevalent over the years as it can be easily scaled and deployed in large organizations. However, much attention has been drawn to this technology because of the many security threats that challenges it and as such, we intend to explore these vulnerabilities and the mitigation techniques for them, while enumerating possible ways of improving such solutions and finding common grounds among these solutions.

The understanding of this will aid in wireless network forensics as well. However, network forensics deals with the capture, recording and analysis of network events in order to discover evidential information about the source of security attacks in a court of law [10].

[2] BACKGROUND

The fact that wireless networks are cheap and easy to make available has peaked the interest of people in its deployment. WLAN allows clients to be able to send large files, access the internet and large bandwidth without the need for cables [2]. According to WiFi alliance (which is actually the organization that owns the WiFi) defines WiFi as any “wireless local area network (WLAN) products that are based on the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineer’ (IEEE) 802.11 standards.” It is worthy of note to mention that WiFi does not mean “Wireless Fidelity” but the IEEE 802.11x standard as defined by the IEEE community. WiFi works with no physical wired connection between sender and receiver by using radio frequency (RF) technology, a frequency within the electromagnetic spectrum associated with radio wave propagation [2]

The image below shows a sample wireless network system along with some components of such systems.

Fig.1 showing the various components of a wireless LAN setup

Before we proceed, it is expedient we know how a typical wireless network actually functions in terms of how a new network entity connects to or accesses the network.

A WiFi client passes through different five stages or processes before it is fully associated with a wireless network; these stages are scanning, joining, authentication, association and re-association [3]. When a new client wants to join the network, it first scans for available networks which are managed by wireless access points (AP). The client then decides which of the available networks to join; this is the joining phase. There exist two main categories of wireless networks: BSS (Basic Service Set) and ESS (Extended Service Set) [3]. In a BSS system, the network only has one wireless access point and the ESS is a rather bigger network with various access points that are usually interconnected. The next step is authentication; where the client has to meet certain criteria before it can be allowed access to the network. The client can either manually select an access point to connect to or choose the access point with the strongest signal strength amidst the available options. [3] Wireless authentication is a method of security on a wireless network. In this phase the station is authenticated using an authentication

server. The station and the AP have to authenticate mutually in order for the station to escape false access points and for the access points to escape false stations.

After the client has been successfully authenticated by the authentication server, it can then be allowed to be associated with the network; this is the association phase in the process. It is at this stage that the client actually gets connected to the network. In a system with ESS, if the client notices an access point with a rather stronger signal strength than the one it's currently associated with, then it can do a re-association; there will be no need to start from the scanning process all over again. This is how new clients get to join a wireless network.

The diagram below shows the process of client authentication [3]

Fig.2 showing the different phases of client authentication into a wireless network

A wireless network can consist of different components. Examples of such components include a wireless access point, wireless network interface card (NIC) and wireless repeaters. In a wireless network, the access point acts as the central processing unit; that is every client that wants to actually join the network has to do so through the access point. Hence, the access point is like the most vital component of a wireless system. The NIC is the component of a client, a laptop for example, that acts as the radio transmitter and receiver for that particular client. Just as in a wired network a physical cable connection is needed, in a wireless network, a NIC is essential for a client to be able to connect to the network. As attenuation is inevitable as distance comes in between the access point and clients, a repeater might be used to further amplify the network signal strength so that the signals are not lost as it propagates through the air.

[3] SECURITY REQUIREMENTS IN WIRELESS NETWORKS

Wireless communications are by nature more vulnerable to a number of different attacks such as man-in-the-middle, DoS and replay [5]

Considering the fact that there are lots of vulnerabilities in a wireless network system, there are basically some standard requirements that every wireless network should be able to guarantee.

However, it should be noted that the two major factors contributing to these problems include [6] Channel, Mobility and Accessibility. As noted earlier in section X that wireless signals are sent through radio waves, this makes such

channel communication susceptible to attacks like eavesdropping. Also, owing to the portability and flexibility advantage attributed to wireless networks, the location of a wireless device can be easily tracked, for instance, thus leading to privacy concerns among the users of such devices. In terms of accessibility, a network device might be connected to the network from a remote location and unmanaged; an attacker can easily take hold of this device and gain access to the network illegitimately.

Systems with wireless networks generally transfer and share data between authorized users; however, this cannot be guaranteed always as attackers can also deceptively participate in network communication. Therefore, a wireless network system must be able to meet some security requirements like data authenticity, confidentiality, integrity and availability [7].

Authenticity: With authenticity, we mean that clients in a wireless network should be mapped to only authorized users. This means that only clients that have been successfully authenticated and associated with the network should be allowed; and any deviation rejected. The MAC address of the clients' wireless NIC can be used for the purpose of ensuring authenticity

Confidentiality: With confidentiality, we mean that only users who the data being communicated is meant for should see it. A simple mechanism that ensures this is encryption and decryption. The sender encrypts the plain-text that is to be sent using some sort of algorithm and then the receiver decrypts the cipher-text using a private that would be shared with him, in the case of a symmetric encryption. This is one way confidentiality can be

ensured in wireless network systems

Integrity: With integrity in mind, we mean that the system should guarantee that the same data that is sent from the source is what is actually received by the destination. If an attacker is able to modify the data while in transit, then integrity has been violated.

Availability: The last security requirement, which is availability simply means that users that are legitimate are able to access the network anytime they want to. If, for example, an attacker is able to launch a DoS (Denial of Service) attack, then this is violated.

[4] WIFI SECURITY PROTOCOLS

WiFi security protocols have been designed to protect wireless network systems, with each having their own strengths and weaknesses. The protocols are WEP, WPA and WPA2

WEP (Wired Equivalent Privacy):

It is part of IEEE 802.11 standard. The purpose of this protocol is to protect link level throughout the wireless signal's communication. It is worthy of mention that this was the first cryptographic protocol that was developed to enable WiFi privacy and security. WEP uses the shared key authentication mechanism and is based on a secret cryptographic key [2]. WEP actually uses the RC4 (Rivest Cipher4) algorithm for its encryption that prevents potential eavesdropping from happening. The algorithm does not employ any form of key management nor replay attack detection, making it very weak in reality. The secret key used in WEP algorithm is 40-bit long with a 24-bit Initialization Vector (IV) that is concatenated to it for acting as the encryption/decryption key [3]. Some of the key weaknesses of the WEP protocol were its inability to prevent the forgery of packets, lack of proper key management, lack of the ability to prevent replay attacks and ultimately, it's easy reuse of Initialization Vectors.

WPA

WPA and WPA2 are two security protocols developed by WI-FI Alliance in 2003 [3] The purpose of the WPA is to solve the downside of the cryptographic mode employed by WEP. WPA and WPA2 have two ways of operation: (Personal and Enterprise)

The Personal method uses the pre-shared key for authentication. However, the Enterprise method involves the use of IEEE 802.1X and EAP.

The WPA has two major variations: AES and TKIP, with the AES being a stronger encryption protocol than the counterpart RC4 that is used in the WEP protocol. TKIP actually makes use of the RC4 mechanism and this makes it backward compatible with the WEP protocol. The WPA-Enterprise was designed for enterprise networks, where the EAP provides a stronger authentication method [3]

WPA2

This is the protocol that has officially replaced the earlier WPA design. It employs the use of the AES algorithm and combines that with Counter Mode with Cipher Block Chaining Message (CCMP) to guarantee an even higher level of security to wireless networks. WPA2 uses EAP and a RADIUS server for centralized client authentication using multiple authentication methods such as token cards, Kerberos, and certificates [9].

[5] WIFI SECURITY THREATS

The diagram below shows the different layers in the TCP/IP model, delineating the various levels that data communication pass through from a sender to a receiver, in this case from Node A to Node B. ([1] fig 2)

Fig. 3 showing how data is transferred from the sender node to the receiver node, across each layer

Generally speaking, we can classify WiFi security attacks into Active Attacks and Passive Attacks. In active attacks, the attacker change the contents of the information and generate fake information in the network to destroy network security like Unauthorized Access, Active Eavesdropping, Man in the Middle Attack (MITM), Session Hijacking, Denial of Service, Replay, while in Passive Attacks, the attacker just listen to the traffic of the network, obtain information from the packets without changing it like passive Eavesdropping and Traffic Analysis [4]. It is worthy of mention that active attacks are sort of easier to detect as compared to passive attacks. In general, network attacks take four major styles, namely Snooping, Modification, Masquerading, and Denial of Service [3]

Snooping: This is where an attacker disguises as a well known and trusted member of a network. With this, sensitive information about an organization can be accessed or stolen, security walls can be easily bypassed and the attacker can easily implant malware on the network.

Modification: With the attacker now having access to the data of interest, data modification means the attacker altering the data or its contents without the knowledge of the sender; for instance, the destination IP address of the data can be changed by the attacker

Masquerading: If an attacker, for instance, has access to the login details of an employee of an organization, the attacker can use these login details to get access to the network, masquerading the legitimate owner of those details.

Denial of Service: With DoS attacks, the intention of the attacker is to prevent others from accessing the network service of interest, by keeping such service busy through packet flooding.

Now, we proceed to take an in depth look at the security attacks that exist at each layer of the OSI (Open System Interconnect) model.

The table below gives an overview of the main protocols and specifications of the wireless OSI Layers [1] #Table II from [1]

OSI Layers	Main Protocols and Specifications
Application	HTTP, FTP, SMTP [62]
Transport	TCP, UDP [63], [64]
Network	IP, ICMP [65]
MAC	CSMA/CA, ALOHA, CDMA [66], OFDMA [67]
PHY	Transmission Medium, Coding and Modulation

Fig.4 showing the main protocols of the various OSI model layers

Physical-Layer Attacks: Out of the layers in the OSI model, this is the lowermost level. It represents the part of the OSI model we can interact with physically, such as the cat5 connecting cables. Since wireless networks perform data communication using broadcast, it makes this layer quite vulnerable to two main attacks: eavesdropping and jamming. With eavesdropping, the attacker attempts to actually see the message that is being communicated between two nodes on the network - to this effect, a secret key is used for the purpose of encryption and decryption. With jamming, the attacker uses a device on the network to induce interference into the network, preventing others from accessing network resources.

MAC-Layer Attacks: This is the layer that deals with the Network Interface Card (NIC). The NIC is hardcoded into the nodes in a network, however, this can still be manually altered by an attacker. In this case, using the new MAC address, the attacker can pretend to be a legitimate node on the network and either access network resources or prevent others from accessing network resources.

Network-Layer Attacks: Since the main protocol in this layer is the Internet Protocol (IP) address, the attacks at this layer are primarily targeted towards nodes' IP addresses. An attacker can successfully intercept data communication between two nodes, capture the IP address of one of the nodes and then pretend to be one of the legitimate nodes by using its IP address. With this, communications between network routers, for example, can be intercepted by the attacker and sensitive information accessed. Also, the attacker can cause network nodes to send massive traffic to another node of interest.

Transport-Layer Attacks: There are two main protocols at this level - Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and User Datagram Protocol (UDP). With TCP, the connection is guaranteed to be reliable as this is a characteristic of TCP, and examples of TCP communication include Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP). Therefore, this level can be exploited by an attacker initiating massive ICMP requests on the network, since the receiving node is bound to send back the ICMP response - this can have an enormous impact on the network resources. With UDP, reliable data transfer is not guaranteed, but the latency of transmission is greatly reduced, and this is why UDP is majorly used in video transmissions. With massive UDP packets generated on the network, the attacker can also succeed in exploiting this protocol.

Application-Layer Attacks: This layer has three main protocols - HyperText Transfer Protocol (HTTP) for web services, File Transfer Protocol (FTP) for file transfer and Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) for email communication. The main HTTP attacks include the Malware attack (e.g., Trojan horse, viruses, worms, backdoors, keyloggers, etc.), structured query language (SQL) injection attack and cross-site scripting attack [10].

[6] MITIGATION AGAINST THESE ATTACKS

Now we approach the conclusion of this work by taking a good look at the various security mechanisms designed to mitigate these attacks.

The first consideration here will be the use of Firewall technology. A firewall is basically a set of instructions defining what type of traffic is allowed to either exit the network or enter the network. Examples of firewall rules could be as simple as stating the list of IP or MAC addresses that should not be granted access to the network due to past events. It should however be noted that a firewall could also be a hardware device that allows the configuration of these rules.

Another consideration that can be put in place is the actual use of encryption and decryption technologies. Here, the plain text being transferred is encrypted at the sender end using a private key and decrypted at the receiver's end using the same. This has been built into many wireless network devices by default as a measure against wireless attacks.

Training and educating the users about network security is also of paramount importance. It is often observed that end users do not know how to implement security and leaves various loopholes for attackers [4]. It is a well-established fact that before an attacker can access a network, it has to first scan for available broadcast SSID. Thus, turning off this characteristic could prevent the particular access point of interest from being seen by attackers who might want to associate with it.

The last point of consideration here is the use of virtual private networks (VPN). With a VPN, an organization has an encrypted data communication channel through which data can be security transferred over the internet; this means that both the messages being transmitted and the transmission channel are both well secured from being attacked.

We can observe that these security measures rely on the upper OSI layers, with little consideration given to the physical layer, which exposes the wireless network to attacks. Hence, we take a brief look at the measures taken to protect this layer from attacks.

The first is Artificial Noise Aided Security, which allows the source node to generate specific interfering signals termed as artificial noise so that only the eavesdropper is affected adversely by the interfering signals, while the intended destination node remains unaffected [1]. However, this method was designed with less consideration for Quality of Service (QoS); thus, a system that utilizes this method primarily to also make a better QoS would be deemed more effective.

A second consideration is the use of security-oriented beamforming techniques which allows the source node to transmit its information signal in a particular direction to the legitimate destination node, so that the signal received at an eavesdropper (that typically lies in a direction different from the destination node) experiences destructive interference and hence becomes weak [1].

[7] COMMON GROUNDS AMONG THESE TECHNIQUES

Having considered some of the mitigation techniques against the security threats faced by wireless networks, we can easily say that; a mitigation technique should not just be focused on network security alone without proper consideration for its impacts on other areas of the network. Considering Quality of Service (QoS), for example, a mitigation technique should be such that the QoS does not get negatively impacted while security is enhanced. In addition, any technique for threat mitigation should have ease of deployment as a good feature; because the effectiveness of a security technique can be dampened if it is not easy to deploy. Lastly, security mechanisms should be able to be used in any network device. For instance, if a measure is targeted at security wireless routers, then this technique should be compatible with existing routing devices, and not just a few of them.

[8] CONCLUSION

In this work, we have taken a careful look at what a network is, and particularly what a wireless network is and its various main components. We then look at the various phases a client passes through in order for it to be successfully allowed access into a wireless network of interest. We emphasized that the major security threats in WiFi are snooping, modification, masquerading and Denial of Service.

The different levels of the OSI model were investigated, and the various attacks possible at each layer also mentioned. Mitigation techniques against these threats are provided in section 6, with some comments on how some of these techniques can be improved upon. More discussion was done about the measures that can be taken to counter attacks at the physical layer and the work is concluded by stating some of the many common grounds that exist amidst the techniques for security wireless networks.

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